

Are you willing to assess vulnerability to food fraud?

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Focus

The research work has focused on food fraud vulnerability assessment in food supplements supply chain.

Research approach

- Method: Desk research (secondary research)

(a research method that involves using already existing data)

- Research area: EU
- The case of food supplements supply chain

The major sources of information on non-compliance with EU food law

- the EU Food Fraud Network & Administrative Assistance and Cooperation System (EU FFN & AAC)
 - the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF)
 - HorizonScan
- MedISys-FF (publically online available); over a 6-year period (2015–2020), the system has collected 4375 articles on food fraud incidents from 164 countries in 41 different languages) (Marvin et al., 2022)

These databases evolve from the joint activities of governments and the private sector, and via emergent digital tools that gather data from multiple sources, including information from official food controls, the broadly defined media and peer-review articles.

The aforementioned systems might be used in horizon scanning

- Horizon scanning is a forward-thinking methodology that can be generally applied to improve either institutional planning or policy making where the focus is on potential future situations, hazards or opportunities' i.e. horizon scanning tools have properties which allow for forecasting and prediction (Food and Agriculture Programme (FAO) 2013).

The findings were published

1. Kowalska, A., Bieniek, M., & Manning, L. (2019). Food supplements' non-conformity in Europe – Poland: A case study. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 93, 262-270
2. Manning, L., Bieniek, M., Kowalska, A., & Ward, R. (2021). Dietary supplements, harm associated with synthetic adulterants and potential governance solutions. *Crime Law and Social Change*.

Let's recall some key definitions!

The issue of food fraud

- **Food fraud** is illegal deception conducted for economic gain (Spink, Bedard, Keogh, Moyer, Scimeca, & Vasanet, 2019)
- Previous studies have shown that food fraud is associated with a large variety of food products and the fraud type may vary from deliberate changing of the food product (i.e. substitution, adulteration, dilution etc.) to the manipulation of documents.
- Globally, most common targets for adulteration or fraud are: meat and meat products, seafood, spices and herbs, olive oil (cereal and bakery products in Poland (!)).

A case exchanged in the **EU Food Fraud Network & Administrative Assistance and Cooperation System (EU FFN & AAC)**

is considered as **food fraud** when matches all 4 criteria:

- (1) violation of EU law
- (2) intention
- (3) economic gain
- (4) deception of customers.

The other exchanged cases are considered as non-compliance.

Vulnerability

- **Vulnerability** is a weakness or flaw that creates opportunities for undesirable events related to the system (Spink, Ortega, Chen, & Wu, 2017).
- **Vulnerability** is the extent to which an individual, organization, supply chain or national food system is at risk from, or susceptible to, attack, emotional injury or physical harm, or damage from intentional illicit activity (Manning, & Soon, 2019).

Food quality

A direct consequence of food adulteration and food fraud is a decrease in its quality as well as misleading the purchaser which violates food law provisions.

Food supplements

Directive 2002/46/EC on the approximation of the laws relating to food supplements states that

„**food supplements** are foodstuffs the purpose of which is to supplement the normal diet and which are concentrated sources of nutrients or other substances with a nutritional or physiological effect, alone or in combination, marketed in dose form, namely forms such as capsules, pastilles, tablets, pills and other similar forms, sachets of powder, ampoules of liquids, drop dispensing bottles, and other similar forms of liquids and powders designed to be taken in measured small unit quantities”

Dietary supplement

The **US** Federal Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act Section 321 states that

- „**dietary supplement** means a product (other than tobacco) intended to supplement the diet that bears or contains one or more of the following dietary ingredients: (A) a vitamin; (B) a mineral; (C) an herb or other botanical; (D) an amino acid; (E) a dietary substance for use by man to supplement the diet by increasing the total dietary intake; or (F) a concentrate, metabolite, constituent, extract, or combination of any ingredient described in clause (A), (B), (C), (D), or (E)”

Dietary supplement

The US Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act of 1994 defines

„a **dietary supplement** as a product that: is intended to supplement the diet, contains one or more dietary ingredients, is intended to be taken by mouth as a pill, capsule, tablet or liquid and is labelled on the front panel as being a dietary supplement.”

Questions arise as to...

Are food supplements relatively more vulnerable to deceptive practices?

Why?

Food Fraud and Administrative Assistance (FF AA) cases per product category

Source: [Kowalska, A., Bieniek, M., & Manning, L. \(2019\). Food supplements' non-conformity in Europe – Poland: A case study. Trends in Food Science & Technology, 93, 262-270.](#)

COMMENT

- In 2017 and 2018, '**dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods**' was the most frequently reported non-compliant product category in the EU FFN & AAC System.
- A side note: the AAC works on a voluntary basis (differently from the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed, RASFF) and only for cross-border non-compliances.

Cases associated with dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods **per type of violation** exchanged within the EU FFN & AAC System in 2018

MISLABELLING...

- In 2018, most of the irregularities reported and associated with dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods (77%) were related to **mislabelling**.
- Mislabelling, if intentional is one form of food adulteration, and denies a consumer their right to make an informed choice.

MAJOR AREAS OF NON-COMPLIANCE

- **final composition of the product** (31%)
 - **nutrition/ health claims** (29%)
 - **nutrition declaration** (14%)
- See more in Kowalska, A., Bieniek, M., & Manning, L. (2019). Food supplements' non-conformity in Europe – Poland: A case study. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 93, 262-270.

COMMENT

- Such commercial practices are definitely misleading because they promote false claims or false information on the composition and nutrients and health benefits of the product.
- False claims about the innate and attributed characteristics of the product are likely to lead to the consumer taking a transactional decision that he/she would not have otherwise taken (Kowalska, Bieniek, & Manning, 2019).

RASFF

- One significant element of food safety supervision in the EU is the RASFF System, where the organizations that are responsible for official food controls in the MSs submit notifications on potential hazards and threats, which in many cases result in the withdrawal of unsafe or illegal products from the market.
- RASFF data is useful for food fraud vulnerability assessment where historical evidence of food fraud is perceived as one of the factors influencing the rationalisation and motivation of potential fraudsters (van Ruth, Huisman & Luning, 2017).

Total number of **RASFF notifications** for dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods

COMMENT

- In our case study, the sampling is not representative that has given rise to the dataset and the time series is short which is why using a trend analysis to draw objective conclusions may be questionable.
- However, the considered data demonstrates limited variation and a clear increasing tendency, and therefore a linear trend can be estimated.
- Analysis of the RASFF database demonstrates that **the number of food safety issues identified by RASFF notifications associated with dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods has a growing trend since 2004.**

Food fraud vulnerability (FFV) concept by van Ruth, Huisman, & Luning (2017)

- The authors framed food fraud vulnerability with a criminological theory and identified key factors that added to the vulnerability (susceptibility) to fraud.

FFV can be defined by 3 elements:

- **opportunities** (suitable target),
- **motivations** (motivated offender) and
- **control measures** (guardianship).

Food fraud vulnerability concept by van Ruth, Huisman, & Luning (2017) can be illustrated as follows:

COMMENT

- The **opportunities** point out why offenders are able to commit fraud.
- The **motivations** detail why offenders would want to commit fraud.
- The **control measures** in place may counteract the vulnerability resulting from opportunities and motivations.

The example of food supplements supply chain

OPPORTUNITIES - 1

- **The complexity of** dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods and innate variability of products' composition adds to analytical testing complexity so the products might be more vulnerable to deceptive practices as a result (Diuzheva et al. 2018).

OPPORTUNITIES - 2

MOTIVATIONS - 1

- Historical evidence of fraud in food supplements' supply chain (AAC data, RASFF database) is perceived as one of the factors influencing the motivation of potential fraudsters.
- **Former illicit behaviour** in certain industries potentially increase the vulnerability to fraud (van Ruth, Huisman, & Luning, 2017).

And now...

Let's use the specific case of food supplements' non-compliance in Poland as the lens of enquiry.

Let's look at the market capacity for dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods.

Number of **new notifications** of dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods, to the Chief Sanitary Inspector (GIS) in Poland

COMMENT

- Average annual growth rate (AAGR) of new notifications within the studied period 2007-2018 is equal to 25.1%.
- **The market** has been growing tremendously!
- There were about **60,000** food supplements and fortified foods on the Polish market in 2018 (GIS, 2018).

Another fact is that...

- Over the period 1997-2005, **sales of food supplements in Poland increased in real terms by 219%**, the highest level in the EU (Kotynia, Szewczyk, & Tuzikiewicz-Gnitecka, 2017).

What contributes to the growth of the food supplements' market in Poland?

- The way to enter the food supplements market in Poland is extremely easy.
- To enter the Polish market, suppliers must notify the Chief Sanitary Inspector (GIS) via an electronic system about placing dietetic food, food supplement or fortified food on the market and also provide a sample of the product packaging.
- There is no fee for it.

What contributes to the growth of the food supplements' market in Poland?

- A survey conducted by TNS Poland in 2014, on a representative sample of adult residents in Poland (n=1000), shows that **41% of respondents attribute medicinal properties to food supplements.**
- 50% of these respondents believe that food supplements are subject to the same regulatory controls as synthetic drugs with only 27% of respondents correctly describing food supplements as foodstuffs intended to supplement the normal diet, and alarmingly 25% of those surveyed believed that there was no unsafe dose of a food supplement (Kozłowska-Wojciechowska, 2014; SCO, 2017).

What contributes to the growth of the food supplements' market in Poland?

- High prices of drugs,
- very long queues or extremely long waiting times for a specialist doctor's appointment

influence Polish citizens' growing interest in food supplements

(Stepurko, Pavlova, & Groot, 2016; Kister, 2018).

MOTIVATIONS - 2

- **High level of competition (pressure) in the industry** increases the motivation of potential perpetrators to take advantage of deceptive behavior for economic gain.

MOTIVATIONS - 3

- Moreover, “discount pharmacies” are getting more and more popular in Poland and emerging **price asymmetries** between legitimate and illicit sources could act as motivating factors influencing the incidence of Economically Motivated Adulteration.

CONTROL MEASURES - 1

- Although the National Sanitary Inspection (PIS) in Poland carries out independent supervision and checks in processing plants regarding the safety and quality of dietetic foods, food supplements and fortified foods, **the size of the market exceeds the control capacities of PIS.**

CONTROL MEASURES - 2

- **The Chief Sanitary Inspector (GIS)** may conduct an investigation to confirm the intrinsic characteristics of the product declared as either food for a specific group, food supplement or fortified food with special attention given to compliance with EU and national food law.
- **In 2018, GIS was overloaded**, with the notification process still pending for over 75% of the notified products that have already entered the Polish market.
- Ca. 40% of the products notified in 2007 have not been checked for 11 years (GIS, 2018).

CONCLUSION

- The absorptive capacity of the food supplements' market in Poland and the extremely easy way to enter the market, impacts on the wider EU harmonized market i.e. **the Polish market may be seen as a “point of entry” to the wider EU market for deceptive food supplement products.**

CONCLUSION

Governance needs to be strengthened both at the EU level where overarching regulation can be introduced and also in individual member states, such as Poland and other countries where

- situational socio-economic factors such as health-care provision
 - and the associated absorptive capacity of the food supplements' market
 - and the ability of national institutions to institute effective governance
- all play a role in creating vulnerability and an economic space for deceptive behaviour to occur.